

Where do Jupiters Live? Investigating the Correlation
between Jupiter Occurrence Rate and Host Star Type

A Thesis Presented

by

Brian Claus

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Abstract

I investigate the observational biases inherent in exoplanet transit surveys and explain the methodology for calculating the planet occurrence rate from a transit survey. I present calculations of the Jupiter type planet occurrence rate around 3 subsets of the Kepler target stars 1)The M Dwarfs 2) The Solar Type (G,K) Stars 3)The High Mass (O,B,A,F) stars. We are unable to provide accurate occurrence rates for the M Dwarfs or the very high mass (O,B) stars due to a prohibitively low number of planet candidate host stars in these populations. However I am able to demonstrate that there is no strong correlation between Jupiter type planet occurrence rate and stellar mass when restricted to the analysis of the G,K stars vs. the A,F stars. If there is correlation between Jupiter type planet occurrence rate and stellar mass it occurs over larger mass ranges and cannot be discovered from the Kepler dataset. Radial velocity surveys as well as future TESS observations of very high mass and low mass stars may be necessary to investigate the existence of a correlation over greater mass ranges.

1 Introduction

The study of extrasolar planets is still a very young field. Methods of detecting exoplanets have only existed for 20 years. Because of this, the biases in exoplanet detection methods are not always well understood or carefully considered. Each new method or improvement in exoplanet detection has dramatically transformed ideas of what types of planets are common and where planets are common. The most recent development in this evolving understanding has been the Kepler transit survey. The thousands of planets Kepler has discovered provide new opportunities for learning about the distribution of planets and where we can find them. The goal of this project is to use this new Kepler data to get a better understanding of where the oldest type of extrasolar planet, the giant Jupiter type planets, are located. Informed by the history of exoplanet discoveries I seek to fully understand the biases inherent in the Kepler survey so that I can use the data properly. In the following sections I will describe the biases inherent in the different exoplanet detection methods and demonstrate why it is so important to understand these biases if one wants to understand

anything about the true population of extrasolar planets.

1.1 Radial Velocity Detection of Exoplanets

The planet that is widely referenced as the first discovered exoplanet is 51 Pegasi b (Mayor & Queloz 1995). Although the existence of extrasolar planets had been expected, the nature of 51 Peg b was surprising. The planet has a mass $\leq 0.472 \pm 0.039 M_J$ and a semi-major axis of 0.0527 ± 0.0030 AU. It was extremely surprising for astronomers to discover a planet with a mass comparable to that of Jupiter but an orbit much closer to its host star than Mercury's orbit. This type of planet, called "Hot Jupiters," was the most commonly detected type of planet for the earliest period of exoplanet studies.

51 Peg b was discovered through the radial velocity detection method. This method detects planets by observing the motion of the planet's host star in response to the planet's movement. A star-single-planet interaction can be modeled as a 2 body system undergoing no net motion. Since the planet is orbiting the star, the star must move in an opposing motion to maintain the position of the center of mass.

$$M_p * V_p + M_* * V_* = 0 \tag{1.1}$$

Where M_p , V_p are the planet's mass and velocity and M_* , V_* are the star's mass and velocity. Therefore, by measuring the periodic motion of the star, an observer can infer the motion of a planet on a periodic orbit. The radial velocity planet detection method involves observing the star's motion along the line of sight by measuring the periodic redshift and blueshift of the star.

Since the signal being measured is a redshift/blueshift, the signal's magnitude is related to the magnitude of V_* . A large value of V_* will produce a large redshift/blueshift, while a small V_* will produce a small redshift/blueshift.

Therefore, the easiest to detect signals will be produced for large values of M_p and V_p . By derivation of V_p , it can be shown that smaller orbits tend to produce larger V_p . An eccentric orbit can complicate the issue, since the part of the orbit close to the star will have a large V_p , and the part of the orbit farther from the star will have a smaller V_p . When considering the simple case of a circular orbit, V_p can be calculated by finding the Keplerian velocity by setting centripetal force and gravitational force equal:

$$V_{keplerian} = \sqrt{\frac{GM_*}{a}} \quad (1.2)$$

Substituting this in for V_p , we find:

$$V_* = M_p \sqrt{\frac{G}{M_* a}} \quad (1.3)$$

So the factors that determine V_* are M_p , M_* , and a (semi-major axis). This shows that if planets were evenly distributed around stars of all different masses, we would expect to detect more planets around the smallest stars. Also, we would expect most of the planets we detect to be very large and very close to their host stars. The poorer our instrumental sensitivity, the more we should expect these types of planets to dominate. In fact, we would expect the easiest detections to be these “Hot Jupiters” like 51 Peg b.

This shows that when using the population of discovered exoplanets to generalize about the entire distribution of planets, it is important to consider the selection effects of our surveys. The fact that the first exoplanets were Hot Jupiters did not reflect the true distribution of planets; it was the result of observational biases.

An additional complication to mention in regards to the radial velocity method is that there is a geometric dependence. If a planet’s orbit is edge-

on with respect to our line of sight, we will observe the full red/blueshift of the star as the planet completes its orbit. But if the orbit is face-on, an observer will not see any radial velocity signal. Intermediate orientations will produce a smaller observed signal according to:

$$V_{observed} = V_* \sin(i) \tag{1.4}$$

Where i is the inclination angle. Inclination is defined with an edge-on orbit as $i = 90$ and a face-on orbit as $i = 0$. $\sin(i)$ is at its minimum at $i = 0$ and its maximum at $i = 90$ so planets with orbital inclination closer to 90 degrees will produce a larger transit signal while planet's with an orbital inclination closer to $i = 0$ degrees will produce a very small signal. Only planet's with sufficiently large $\sin(i)$ will be detectable by a radial velocity survey. It is important to remember this geometric effect and account for undetectable geometries.

Finally, it is important to recognize that in order for the planet signal to be confirmed, the entire redshift/blueshift signal must be observed. This requires the star be observed over the planet's entire orbital period. This is another factor that preferentially selects for planets that are closer to their host stars since they will complete their orbit in a much shorter period. Observing many periods increases confidence that the signal is truly the result of a planet and not just stellar noise adding another factor that biases radial velocity surveys towards the detection of very short period planets.

1.2 Transit Detection of Exoplanets

The other major technique used in exoplanet surveys is the transit method. The idea behind this detection method is to observe the light blocking effect of the planet passing in front of its host star. Detecting a consistent periodic decrease in the amount of light observed from the star can indicate the presence of an

eclipsing object.

The first planet detected by the transit method was HD 209458 b (Charbonneau, 2001). This planet has a mass of $0.71M_J$, a radius of $1.35 \pm 0.05R_J$, a semi-major axis of 0.045 AU, and an orbital period of 84.59 hours (Charbonneau, 2001). This is another example of a planet that is very close to its star and has an extremely short orbital period. Much like the radial velocity detection method, the transit method preferentially detects planets with very short periods. Just like with the radial velocity surveys, more observations of the periodic signal provides us with more confidence that the signal is truly due to a planet rather than just random noise. Typically, transits are observed at least 2 or 3 times before a planet detection is reported.

The actual signal detected by the transit method is a decrease in the amount of light transmitted by the star due to the planet blocking some of that light. This effect is easy to calculate using simple geometry. The fraction of the host star's light blocked is the fraction of the star's surface area being blocked by the planet.

$$L_{observed} = L_{total} * \left(\frac{R_p}{R_*}\right)^2 \quad (1.5)$$

Where L represents luminosity and R_p , R_* are the radius of the planet and star respectively. This means that it is much easier to detect a transit around a smaller star than a larger star. Furthermore, planets with larger radii are significantly easier to detect.

Like the radial velocity method, the transit method also has a geometric dependence on which planets can be observed. In order to be detectable, a planet has to pass in front of the star from the observer's line of sight. For a circular orbit, this is determined by the inclination angle. The range of inclination angles that will produce a planet that passes between the star and the observer are

given by:

$$R_* - R_p \geq a \cos(i) \quad (1.6)$$

There is also a possibility for grazing transit in which only part of the planet passes in front of the star and blocks light. The condition for a grazing transit is:

$$R_* + R_p \geq a \cos(i) \quad (1.7)$$

The fraction of light blocked in a grazing transit is the ratio of the area blocked and the star's total area. Since we can only observe the small fraction of the transits whose orbits are oriented with the correct geometry, we need to understand the probability that a randomly chosen orientation would yield the planet we observe. We can then use that probability to estimate the number of planets we have missed. If there is only a $\frac{1}{50}$ chance that a certain planet we observe would be in an observable orientation, then we can assume that there are approximately 49 planets of this type that we did not observe because they were in other configurations.

For a circular orbit, this probability is relatively easy to calculate. We simply integrate the condition for a transit over inclination and compare it to all the possible values of inclination. This gives us the probability that a given planet will be in a detectable orientation:

$$p_{transit} = \frac{(R_* - R_p)}{a} \quad (1.8)$$

And, allowing for grazing transits:

$$p_{transit} = \frac{(R_* + R_p)}{a} \quad (1.9)$$

This shows that a planet that is close to its star is more likely to be detected not only due to a shorter period allowing for easier observations of repeated transits but also because it is more likely to lie in a favorable geometric orientation. This does somewhat complicate our conclusions with respect to stellar radius: a large stellar radius makes the signal of a transit more difficult to detect but it does increase the chances that a planet will transit at all.

For planets with eccentric orbits the calculation becomes more complicated. Winn (2010) presents the result of the calculation:

$$p_{transit} = \left(\frac{R_* \pm R_p}{a}\right)\left(\frac{1 + e \sin(\omega)}{1 - e^2}\right) \quad (1.10)$$

Where ω is the other angle representing the orientation of the ellipse in space. In most cases it is safe to assume a circular orbit. I will assume circular orbits throughout this work. In addition it is common to neglect R_p since $R_* \gg R_p$. I will make this assumption from here on.

1.3 Overall Selection Effects of RV and Transit Surveys

Overall, both surveys preferentially detect short period planets. Any method that works by detecting a periodic signal will have this bias. In addition, both survey types select for larger planets. A larger RV signal is produced by a planet with a large mass and a larger transit signal is produced by a planet with a large radius.

In addition, there is a bias for smaller host stars. RV signal magnitude is dependent on the ratio between stellar mass and planetary mass, so a smaller star will provide a more favorable ratio and a larger signal. Similarly, the transit signal magnitude is proportional to $(\frac{R_p}{R_*})^2$, so a smaller radius will produce a larger magnitude signal.

Finally, both surveys have geometric components that must be accounted for.

Only very specific geometries will produce a transit signal, and most geometries will decrease the magnitude of a RV signal.

All of these effects must be accounted for in any statistical treatment of the exoplanet population. In my study, I follow the work of Howard et. al. (2012) and Dressing & Charbonneau (2013) which provide a framework for tackling this complex issue in the case of a transit survey. I do not use radial velocity survey data for this study but I do compare my final results to those found in several different radial velocity surveys.

1.4 Kepler Survey

Since the discovery of the first extrasolar planets, there have been a large number of radial velocity surveys as well as transit surveys in order to detect planet candidates for further study. However, it is not until extremely recently with the results of the Kepler survey, that the population of planet candidates has become large enough to perform statistical analysis for the purpose of estimating features of the “true” distribution of planets in the galaxy.

The Kepler telescope is a space based instrument in an Earth-trailing orbit. Before its guidance system malfunctioned in May 2013, the spacecraft was oriented to continuously observe 150,000 main sequence stars. The Kepler telescope continuously measured the brightness of these stars in order to detect the periodic dips in brightness that would indicate a transit event.

The Kepler telescope provided data from May 12th 2009 - May 11th 2013, when a second of four reaction wheels responsible for rotating the telescope malfunctioned. During its operation lifetime, the Kepler telescope discovered over 100 planets and over 3,000 planet candidates. These planet candidates provide an immense amount of data that can be used to constrain the population of planets around the stars Kepler observed. The following graph shows the

Kepler Planet Candidates

Figure 1: Kepler Planet Candidates (Period vs. Radius) as of January 2013. Our analysis is focused on the less common Jupiter type planets.

estimated radius and period of the first 2740 planet candidates discovered by the Kepler team as of January 2013 and presented by the Kepler Team at the 2013 Winter meeting of the American Astronomical Society.

The Kepler survey has shown that for short period planets, Earth and Neptune type planets are in fact much more common than Jupiter type planets. In this project, I study only the Jupiter type planets. I attempt to determine if there is any correlation between host star mass and frequency of Jupiter type planet occurrence.

Although smaller planets appear to be much more common, the Kepler results do include a large number of massive Jupiter type planets that should allow us enough samples to perform a serious statistical analysis. The following bar chart shows the number of Kepler Planet Candidates as of January 2013, sorted into 5 rough bins of increasing planetary size: Earth-size, Super Earth-sized,

Figure 2: Number of Kepler Planet Candidates binned by Radius as of January 2013

Neptune-size, Jupiter-size, and larger than Jupiter.

There are approximately 300 Jupiter type planets in the Kepler data alone. I believe that the Kepler dataset contains sufficient Jupiters to carry out this analysis.

1.5 Planet Formation Theory

The dominant theory of how Jupiter type planets are formed is referred to as the “core accretion model.” The proto-stellar system begins as a cloud of dust and gas orbiting the protostar. Over time, the dust grains collide and stick through electrostatic forces, eventually forming smaller planetesimals. These planetesimals begin to collide, and when the resulting post-collision velocity is low enough, they will stick through gravitational forces and form a larger planetesimal. This process continues until enough planetesimals have joined together to form a protoplanet. When the protoplanet becomes large enough,

it will have a strong enough gravitational potential to begin accreting gas from the surrounding disk.

However, not all planets actually do accrete large amounts of gas. Rocky planets such as Mercury, Earth, Venus, and Mars are planets in our own solar system that did not accrete a significant amount of hydrogen or helium during their formation process.

The stellar wind from the forming protostar eventually blows the gaseous hydrogen and helium out of the protoplanetary disk. A planet can only become a gas giant such as Jupiter if its rocky core grows large enough to accrete gas before the gas is blown away. This is one of the reasons why large planets are believed to form farther from their host star. At further distances from the protostar, the temperature is lower, and therefore more of the protoplanetary disk is in a solid state instead of a gaseous state. More material allows the protoplanetary core to grow faster.

It also logically follows from this theory that a protoplanetary disk that has more material would cause the protoplanetary core to accrete matter more quickly. Since the protostar and the protoplanetary disk all form out of the same cloud, one could also expect a larger star to have had a larger protoplanetary disk. Therefore, one would expect to observe more large gas giant planets around high mass stars than around low mass stars due to there simply being more material available for planet formation in their protoplanetary disks.

This is a very tenuous theoretical framework and could be complicated by any number of factors. However, with a sufficiently large sample of exoplanets to draw from, we should be able to test the final implication of this theory and determine whether there is any correlation between Jupiter type planet occurrence frequency and stellar mass. Investigating this correlation is the goal of this project.

1.6 Other Statistical Studies of Exoplanet Population

1.6.1 Howard 2012

While this work addresses the particular question of Jupiter occurrence rate and stellar mass correlation, there are many other statistical studies of the exoplanet population that can provide a framework for our analysis.

In particular, the Kepler planet candidates have been studied quite heavily. Howard (2012) used the first two quarters of Kepler data to provide a detailed analysis of occurrence rate for planets with a < 0.25 AU around the solar type stars observed by Kepler. This work develops a detailed framework for avoiding the previously described detection biases in the transit method. We will follow this framework for much of our study.

1.6.2 Dressing & Charbonneau 2012

One difficulty with using the Kepler dataset is that the Kepler mission is primarily concerned with planets around solar type stars. The Kepler team provides stellar parameters for all of the Kepler target stars, but these parameters are based on models that assume each star is solar type. Therefore, most of the small mass stars and high mass stars are poorly characterized, and this error extends to many of the planet characterizations that depend on host star characteristics. For example, planet radius is determined by equating the percent of light blocked during transit with the $(\frac{R_p}{R_t})^2$. An incorrect estimate of the stellar radius would therefore give an incorrect estimate for the planet's radius. In order to determine the true occurrence rate for Jupiter type planets, we need to find the correct stellar parameters.

Fortunately, this work has been done for the smaller stars, the M Dwarfs. Using Dartmouth stellar models and the Kepler photometry, Dressing and Charbonneau were able to provide corrected stellar parameters for the cool Ke-

Corrections to Kepler Input Catalog

Figure 3: Shows Kepler Input Catalog Original Temperature and Radius vs Corrected Values. This is Table 4 of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013)

pler target stars (Dressing & Charbonneau 2012). They determine a set of 3897 stars with temperatures below 4000 K as the set of M Dwarfs. They then use these revised stellar parameters to provide revised radii of the planet candidates around the M Dwarfs. They also provide a calculation of the planetary occurrence rate around M Dwarfs using a similar methodology to that provided in Howard 2012. Figure 4 from Dressing & Charbonneau shows the original Kepler team radius and temperatures for these stars as well as their revised values:

Dressing & Charbonneau determine that their set of 3897 M dwarfs contains 64 stars hosting at least one exoplanet candidate and 95 total exoplanet candidates. They divide the candidates into 4 categories:

$$0.5R_{\oplus} < R_p \text{ (1 candidate)}$$

$$0.5R_{\oplus} < R_p < 1.4R_{\oplus} \text{ (47 candidates)}$$

$$1.4R_{\oplus} < R_p < 4R_{\oplus} \text{ (43 candidates)}$$

$$R_p > 4R_{\oplus} \text{ (4 candidates)}$$

Of the final category of large radius planet candidates, 3 have radii consistent with a Jupiter type planet ($10.74_{-1.44}^{+0.98}$, $17.12_{-2.48}^{+2.48}$, $11.32_{-1.29}^{+1.22}$) and one has a radius more consistent with a Neptune type planet ($4.77_{-0.69}^{+0.63}$). It is important to note that the Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) analysis only classified the stars that had been observed at that time. We can use their classification for any star that was observed in the first 6 quarters, but stars that were first observed after that are not classified in their 2013 paper.

1.6.3 Radial Velocity Surveys

This project performed a study of the Hot Jupiter occurrence rate around nearby solar type stars using data from the California Planet Search (Wright et. al. 2012). They report an occurrence rate of $1.2 \pm 0.38\%$. Several other notable radial velocity surveys that performed this calculation include Marcy et. al. 2005, which observed 1330 stars and found a Jupiter occurrence rate of $1.2 \pm 0.1\%$, and Mayor et. al. 2011, which used HARPS data and found a Hot Jupiter occurrence rate of $0.89 \pm 0.36\%$. There are a large number of different radial velocity surveys that have been used to calculate occurrence rates such as the one we are looking for in this project. Although we will primarily rely on Kepler data, we will supplement it with data from radial velocity surveys whenever possible.

1.6.4 Morton & Johnson 2011

One important issue to consider when using data from transit surveys is the possibility of false positives. Any phenomenon that produces a periodic obstruction of the host star could impersonate a transit. Morton & Johnson (2011) determines the false positive rate for various scenarios, including the chance that a given transit is actually an eclipsing binary or hierarchical triple. Their overall conclusions state that false positive probability has a strong dependence

on stellar brightness and galactic latitude as well as a weak dependence on transit depth. Almost all of the planet candidates have a false positive probability $< 10\%$, and most candidates have false positive probability $< 5\%$. Both the Howard and Dressing papers reference this result. They state that it shows the false positive rate is too low to have an effect on the overall statistical analysis. However, since this work deals exclusively with Jupiter type planets, false positive probability may be very important to consider. False positive probabilities are on average quite low, but are significantly higher for large Jupiter type planets.

1.7 Statistical Framework

Due to the many systematic biases involved in radial velocity and transit surveys, we need to carefully construct our statistical framework in order to ensure that we are not biasing our results. We will follow the basic framework used by Howard 2012 and (Dressing & Charbonneau 2012). The basic idea is to calculate the number of stars searched around which a certain planet could have been detected but was not.

1. Take one planet observed in the survey
2. Artificially place that planet around each star from the survey
3. Determine for each star whether that planet could be detected around it
4. Calculate the overall occurrence rate for that planet using the number of stars it could have been detected around
5. Correct for geometric orientation effects
6. Repeat for each planet
7. Use occurrence rate for each planet to construct an overall occurrence rate

This is the general framework. In Chapters 2 and 3, I will discuss the implementation in more detail.

Our final goal is to determine whether there is any correlation between stellar mass and Jupiter occurrence rate. So we will separate our target stars into three categories: M Dwarf stars, solar type stars (G,K stars), and high mass stars (O,B,A,F stars). We will calculate the Jupiter occurrence for each category and then determine if there is any statistically significant correlation.

2 Occurrence Rate Calculation

Planet occurrence rate is an intrinsic property of a population of stars. It describes the number of planets per star in that population. A planet occurrence rate of 1 means that on average there is one planet for each star. We can also calculate the planet occurrence rate for a particular type of planet. We could calculate the occurrence rate of planets with period < 100 days, or with radii $< 4R_{\oplus}$. For now, we will describe the procedure for calculating an overall occurrence rate for all planets detected in a transit survey.

Consider the case of a transit survey that has a perfect planet detection rate, meaning that it detects every planet that exists around its target stars. If this survey detected one planet, we could conclude the planet occurrence rate for that population of stars is:

$$occurrence\ rate = \frac{1}{N_*} \tag{2.1}$$

Where N_* is the number of stars observed by the transit survey. For example, consider the case of $N_* = 100$. This would mean that we observed 100 stars and only found one planet. We could then conclude that the abundance of planets in that stellar population is 1 planet per 100 stars.

If this survey had instead detected 2 planets, the planet occurrence rate would be twice as high (2 planets per 100 stars), and if it had detected 10 planets the planet occurrence rate would have been 10 times as high (10 planets per 100 stars). We can generalize this in a simple formula :

$$occurrence\ rate = \frac{planets\ detected}{stars\ searched} = \frac{N_p}{N_*} \quad (2.2)$$

Where N_p is the number of planets detected by the transit survey. Note that equation 2.1 is the formula for a transit survey that has a perfect planet detection rate. It does not accurately describe the method for calculating the planet occurrence rate for a real transit survey with an imperfect planet detection rate. In the following sections, we will explain the correction factors required to apply this formula to an imperfect transit survey, with emphasis placed on the Kepler survey.

2.1 Stars Searched

In equation 2.1, N_* represents all the stars observed in the survey. Since this survey detects any planet around the stars it observes N_* is simply the number of stars observed by the survey. However, if our detection rate is imperfect, there will be some stars for which we will not be able to detect a planet transiting them. Let's return to the case in which we observe 100 stars and find 1 planet. Let's further assume that our 1 planet was found around a very quiet star, one that has very little variation in its brightness. The transit signal will cause a decrease in the brightness of the star that will be quite easy to measure. If that star had been more active and exhibited greater variations in its, brightness it would have been more difficult to observe the planet's transit signal.

Now, when we think about N_* for this survey, can we include the very noisy stars? It isn't fair to say that we searched 100 stars and found 1 planet if

some of those stars were too noisy for us to make any detections of possible planets transiting around them. Therefore we can only include in N_* the stars around which a detection of this transit would have been possible. We must take our 1 observed planet, compare it to each star in the survey and determine if this planet’s transit would have been observable around that star. We ask ourselves the question: If this planet were orbiting that star, would our survey have detected it? If the answer is yes, we can include that star in N_* , but if the answer is no, we must exclude that star from N_* .

The best way to determine whether the planet would have been detected is to use the same detection cutoff that we use to determine which signals are planet candidates, and then test if the planet would make the cutoff. The Kepler detection cutoff is $S/N > 7.1\sigma$. We can estimate the S/N of a planet transiting any star in order to see if that planet would have been detectable around that star. In order to estimate S/N , we need to estimate the signal and the noise. First, we will describe how we estimate the signal, and then we will address the issue of estimating the noise.

2.1.1 Estimating Signal

The signal of a planetary transit is the light it blocks from the star. We detect the fractional change in the star’s light which is equal to the fraction of the star’s area the planet blocks. This magnitude of this signal is referred to as the transit depth and is commonly denoted as δ . The formula for estimating transit depth is:

$$\delta = \left(\frac{R_p}{R_*}\right)^2 \tag{2.3}$$

Where R_p is the planet radius and R_* is the stellar radius. Note that this also is a reason why we must consider each star individually to determine if the

planet would have been detectable around that star. A star’s radius directly impacts the magnitude of the transit signal; the same planet will produce a larger transit depth if it is transiting a small star than if it is transiting a small star.

2.1.2 Estimating Noise

Estimating the stellar noise is more open to multiple methodologies. In our analysis, we use the methodology employed in Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) for estimating stellar noise. The Kepler team provides an estimate of the stellar noise over a specific time period, referred to as the Combined Differential Photometric Precision and frequently written as σ_{CDPP} . The Kepler team provides CDPP for 3,6, and 12 hour durations, which I will refer to as σ_{CDPP3} , σ_{CDPP6} , σ_{CDPP12} . It is important that this estimate of stellar noise is provided for different timescales. The relevant noise for determining our transit S/N is the noise that occurs on the timescale of the transit duration.

We can use the 3 σ_{CDPP} values provided by the Kepler team to estimate noise for any timeframe. We follow the procedure of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) and use a linear interpolation to estimate the noise on the timescale of the transit duration.

Finally, the S/N is also affected by the number of transits we observe. The S/N is proportional to the square root of the number of transits. In simulating the S/N for a hypothetical transit event, we estimate the number of transits by:

$$N_{transits} = \frac{\text{time star observed}}{\text{planet period}} \tag{2.4}$$

Note that this simplistic estimate of the number of transits does not take into account the spacing of gaps in the observation time. This formula is a

simplification that treats all of the observing time as one continuous block. In reality, the observing time is punctuated by many gaps, and it is possible that transits may have taken place during those gap periods, reducing the actual number of transits that could have been observed. This is a complication that was not addressed in Dressing, Charbonneau 2013, and we similarly do not address it.

In total the estimated S/N for a planet around any star from the survey is:

$$S/N = \frac{\delta}{\sigma_{CDPP}} * \sqrt{N_{transits}} \quad (2.5)$$

and a planet is detectable around a star if $S/N > 7.1$.

We calculate equation 2.5 for each planet-star pair; each planet detected by our survey is compared to each star observed in the survey. For each planet, we calculated a number of stars searched (N_*). This is the number of stars around which that particular planet's transit would have been detectable.

It is important to mention what characteristics of the planet we perseve when comparing it to a star. We hold the planet's radius (R_p) and period (P) constant as we compare it to each star. However, the semi-major axis (a) of the planet's orbit changes. As we simulate placing a planet around different stars, it is impossible to perserve both a and R_p . Consider Kepler's 3rd law:

$$P^2 = \frac{4\pi^2 a^3}{G(M_* + M_p)} \quad (2.6)$$

where P and a are the orbital period and semi-major axis respectively, M_* is the mass of the star, M_p is the mass of the planet, and G is the gravitational constant.

When we place our planet around a different star, M_* changes. To accomodate this change either the period, the semi-major axis, or both must change.

We choose to keep the period constant and let the semi-major axis vary as we compare our planet to different stars. We have 2 justifications for this choice.

First, the period of the planets observed is an important limiting factor on the applicability of our occurrence rate. We have only observed planets of a certain period, specifically those with $P <$ the total observing time of our survey * the number of transits we require for a detection. We cannot make predictive statements about planets with periods longer than the time period the survey has observed. For that reason, we do not want to modify the planetary periods when performing this analysis. We are not limited in speaking about semi-major axis in this way. We are able to confidently make predications about the occurrence rate of planets of any semi-major axis as long as their orbital period is within the observing period of our survey.

Second, the planetary period is one of our best measured quantities in planet transit surveys, and typically has very small uncertainties. Because of this, it would be unwise to discard the period in favor of a more poorly measured quantity such as the semi-major axis.

2.2 Geometric Correction Effect

In section 1.2 we stated that the chance of a randomly oriented planetary orbit producing a transit is:

$$p_{transit} = \left(\frac{R_* \pm R_p}{a}\right)\left(\frac{1 + e \sin(w)}{1 - e^2}\right) \quad (2.7)$$

and in the case of a circular orbit eccentricity (e) = 0 and this simplifies to:

$$p_{transit} = \frac{(R_* \pm R_p)}{a} \quad (2.8)$$

Where $R_* + R_p$ include grazing transits in the probability and $R_* - R_p$ does

not include grazing transits. If we assume $R_* \gg R_p$ and neglect the possibility of a grazing transit case, we can again simplify the expression:

$$p_{transit} = \frac{R_*}{a} \quad (2.9)$$

So the chance that we see any given planet transiting is the radius of the host star divided by the semi-major axis of the orbit. We need to consider this transit probability when calculating our planet occurrence rate.

We began our discussion of the geometric correction factor by comparing to the case for a survey that has a perfect planet detection rate; it detects every planet that exists. Real transit surveys are constrained by this geometric transiting probability. For every planet we detect, we are actually only detecting that planet because we are in a lucky position that allows us to detect that planet. For a planet that has $\frac{R_*}{a} = 10$, a randomly placed observer has a 1 out of 10 chance to be located in a position where that transit is detectable. However, we are not a randomly placed observer. We see the planets that are aligned to our position.

But if we assume that planet orbits are distributed in random geometric orientations with respect to us, there should be approximately $1 - \frac{R_*}{a}$ of these planets for every 1 that we detect. If we observe 1 planet with $\frac{R_*}{a} = \frac{1}{10}$, then it is only logical to assume that there are 9 other planets that we did not detect, simply because they are in non-transiting geometric configurations. Therefore there are 10 total planets for every 1 planet we detect that has $\frac{R_*}{a} = \frac{1}{10}$.

In order to find the true planet occurrence rate, and not just the occurrence rate of planets that are aligned for our particular line of sight, we need to multiply by a geometric correction factor equivalent to the inverse of the geometric

probability of transit. Namely:

$$\text{geometric correction factor} = \frac{a}{R_*} \quad (2.10)$$

It is important to note that a is the KOI's semi-major axis around its host star and R_* is the radius of the host star. This term is completely independent of the other stars in the survey; it only incorporates the parameters (a , R_*) associated with the host star.

2.3 Planet Occurrence Rate Formula

With both of these correction factors, we can write the full equation for the planet occurrence rate of a real transit survey. Starting with the case of a single planet detection:

$$\text{occurrence rate single planet} = \frac{1}{N_*} \frac{a}{R_*} \quad (2.11)$$

And we simply sum over all planets for the multiple planet case:

$$\text{occurrence rate} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{planet}} \frac{1}{N_{*i}} \frac{a_i}{R_{*i}} \quad (2.12)$$

This is the full formula for the occurrence rate from an imperfect transit survey, and it is the equation we use to calculate all of the planet occurrence rates that we report in this paper. N_{planet} is the total number of planets detected. For each planet, we calculate a geometric correction factor: the planet's semi-major axis around its host star divided by the host star's radius. We also calculate the number of stars around which a planet of that radius and orbital period would have been detectable, where detectable means that the planet's transit around that star would produce a signal with $S/N > 7.1\sigma$. This number of stars forms the N_{*i} term for that planet.

3 Reproducing Dressing, Charbonneau 2013

3.1 Motivation

For one part of our analysis, we calculate the occurrence rate of Jupiter size planets around the Kepler M Dwarf stars. As mentioned earlier, we needed to use the results of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) to obtain the correct characteristics for these stars. Since they also calculated the occurrence rates for planets around these stars it made sense to begin our analysis here and see if our code could accurately reproduce their results. We followed the procedure of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) and compared our findings to their results. This is the same procedure described in Chapter 2 of this document. This provided a useful check on our code before we applied it to calculating unknown occurrence rates.

3.2 Obtaining Stellar Parameters

First, we needed to determine the population of stars that we would be dealing with for this analysis. We used the stars from Table 1 of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013). These include the updated stellar parameters that accurately reflect the stellar parameters for the M Dwarf Kepler target stars. There are 3897 stars in this sample. For our analysis, we ignored the 5 stars that are part of multiple star systems, bringing our total population of stars down to 3892.

The main stellar parameter that we needed from this table was the stellar radius (R_*). Aside from that, we needed the information about which Kepler target stars are classified as M Dwarfs.

3.3 Obtaining Planet Parameters

Once I have determined which Kepler target stars are M Dwarfs, I should be able to check the Kepler Object of Interest (KOI) database and recover all of the planets that have been discovered around these M Dwarfs. However, since their host stars are misclassified in the Kepler Input Catalog, the planet candidates are misclassified as well. One basic example involves the misclassification of the planet radius. As mentioned previously, transit depth = $(\frac{R_p}{R_*})^2$. One common way of determining the radius of a planet candidate is to measure the transit depth and multiply by the stellar radius $(R_*)^2$. However, if the star is misclassified, R_* will be wrong, and this will propagate to an incorrect value for R_p . Because of this, it is necessary to re-determine planet parameters after reclassifying the stars. Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) provides this data for the planet candidates discovered around the M Dwarfs in the first 6 quarters of Kepler data. We borrow this data from Table 2 of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013). The table contains 95 KOI's. I did not use the 6 KOI's that orbit the multiple star systems, bringing my total number of KOI's to 89.

3.4 Calculating Stars Searched

I followed the description provided in Section 2.1 for determining the number of stars searched for each planet candidate. The transit depth was calculated by taking R_p values from Table 2 of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) and R_* values from Table 1.

I did not calculate the noise values myself. I contacted Dressing directly and obtained the σ_{CDPP} values on the timescale of the transit duration that were used in their analysis. Since the publication of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013), the Kepler team has updated the Kepler data analysis pipeline and reprocessed the transit light curves. Reprocessing the light curves yields updated values for

σ_{CDPP3} , σ_{CDPP6} , and σ_{CDPP12} . The Kepler Input Catalog values for σ_{CDPP} available at present differ from those that were available at the time of the Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) analysis. In order to better compare our results to theirs, I adopted their σ_{CDPP} values. Their values were calculated from σ_{CDPP3} , σ_{CDPP6} , and σ_{CDPP12} using a linear regression to estimate σ_{CDPP} for the timescale of the transit.

I did calculate $N_{transit}$ using different data than the data used in the Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) analysis. At the time of their analysis, there was no online resource for looking up for how long a star was observed. Therefore, it was necessary to determine which quarters a star was in the telescope’s field of view, and use that information to calculate for how long the star was observed. In my reproduction of their analysis, I was able to take advantage of the NASA Exoplanet Archive, which is now able to return a list of quarters for which any star was observed by Kepler. I used this information to determine how long each Kepler target star was observed and then divided by the orbital period to determine $N_{transit}$ for any planet-star pairing.

My results differ from those of Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) in this area. Their more involved method of determining the total time a star was observed seems to have been prone to some error. In some instances, a star was in the telescope’s field of view and scheduled to be observed, but was in fact not observed during that quarter. Therefore, the amount of time many stars were observed was slightly overestimated. With the new data available from the NASA Exoplanet Archive, I have been able to work with Dressing to correct this part of the calculation. Compared to the Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) analysis, my estimates of observed time are lower for several stars, and consequently my number of stars searched (N_*) is 200 stars lower for most KOI’s.

3.5 Calculating Geometric Correction Factors

Calculating the geometric correction factor for each planet requires knowing the semi-major axis of that planet’s orbit (a) and the radius of its host star. Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) Table 2 actually provides $\frac{a}{R_*}$ for each planet, but this value is not used in their actual analysis. The values of $\frac{a}{R_*}$ in table 2 were calculated through fits to the lightcurve. Calculating semi-major axis using Kepler’s 3rd law as we described in section 2.1.2 provides a much more accurate value for a . I follow this methodology, taking the planet’s orbital period and host star radius from Table 2 and using Kepler’s 3rd law to calculate the planet’s semi-major axis around its host star. Then we take $\frac{a}{R_*}$ as the geometric correction factor.

3.6 Results

Table 1 contains a summary of my results for reproducing the Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) results. I present my results as a table listing each planet candidate, its geometric correction, occurrence rate, and number of stars searched (N_*). My geometric correction factors (the number of planets of that type that we infer exist based on the geometric transit probability) are the same as those reported in Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) Figure 15. My occurrence rates are slightly higher due to the previously discussed difference in N_* . If I substitute my value for N_* with the value provided in Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) Table 15, we replicate their occurrence rates, showing that our code is working properly. The only part of the code that has not been directly validated by reproducing the Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) results is the calculation of number of stars searched.

This same code can be applied to my general calculations of giant planet occurrence rates. In the following chapters, I present the use of this code to

analyze the occurrence rate of Jupiter type planets around the solar type, high mass, and M Dwarf Kepler target stars. It is important to mention that, since only 6 quarters of Kepler data were available for the Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) analysis, I have only used 6 quarters of data to produce the results in Table 1. My later analysis of the Jupiter occurrence rate around the M Dwarfs employs the full 17 quarters of Kepler data and will therefore differ from the results for Jupiter type planets in these results.

Table 1: Reproducing Dressing, Charbonneau 2013: Individual KOI Occurrence Rates

KOI	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
247.01	43	0.0166	2675
248.01	24	0.0083	2986
248.02	32	0.010	3135
248.03	12	0.00408	3111
248.04	46	0.016	2906
250.01	39	0.012	3129
250.02	49	0.015	3101
250.03	17	0.0066	2581
250.04	96	0.035	2737
251.01	18	0.0056	3187
251.02	22	0.0153	1452
252.01	47	0.015	3022
253.01	21	0.0067	3199
254.01	11	0.0036	3227
256.01	10	0.0033	3227
463.01	61	0.021	2857

Table 1: continued

KOI	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
531.01	16	0.0051	3224
571.01	25	0.0091	2814
571.02	38	0.013	2860
571.03	16	0.00597	2845
571.04	54	0.0225	2431
596.01	10	0.0036	2930
739.01	7	0.0024	3119
781.01	39	0.012	3105
817.01	59	0.0214	2756
817.02	29	0.010	2851
818.01	32	0.011	2915
854.01	117	0.047	2459
886.01	36	0.013	2796
886.02	48	0.041	1164
886.03	69	0.037	1849
898.01	29	0.0095	3114
898.02	19	0.0063	3070
898.03	48	0.016	2946
899.01	29	0.010	2736
899.02	17	0.00689	2544
899.03	48	0.020	2338
936.01	37	0.012	2940
936.02	7	0.0026	2946
947.01	71	0.025	2806

Table 1: continued

KOI	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
952.01	22	0.0071	3099
952.02	28	0.0096	2995
952.03	54	0.017	3038
952.04	13	0.0046	2964
1078.01	15	0.0048	3117
1078.02	24	0.00774	3144
1078.03	62	0.021	2930
1085.01	25	0.011	2209
1141.01	20	0.0071	2886
1146.01	263	0.012	2183
1164.01	6	0.0025	2642
1201.01	13	0.00489	2872
1393.01	8	0.0027	3197
1397.01	21	0.0071	3091
1427.01	128	0.0043	2922
1649.01	17	0.00689	2602
1681.01	29	0.011	2636
1686.01	140	0.194	726
1702.01	13	0.0053	2562
1843.01	19	0.0067	2844
1843.02	25	0.014	1776
1867.01	12	0.0044	2892
1867.02	40	0.013	3064
1867.03	20	0.0080	2581

Table 1: continued

KOI	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
1868.01	42	0.014	2950
1879.01	62	0.020	2994
1880.01	7	0.0023	3071
1907.01	32	0.011	2966
2006.01	16	0.0085	1869
2036.01	27	0.0095	2892
2036.02	21	0.0085	2520
2057.01	21	0.0083	2597
2058.01	8	0.0030	2880
2090.01	20	0.0070	2894
2130.01	41	0.014	2894
2156.01	14	0.0045	3227
2179.01	47	0.020	2334
2179.02	15	0.0053	2867
2191.01	30	0.016	1910
2238.01	9	0.0032	2793
2306.01	4	0.0014	3021
2329.01	9	0.0032	2930
2347.01	4	0.0014	2964
2418.01	153	0.11	1321
2542.01	12	0.00692	1834
2453.01	6	0.0021	2969
2650.01	857	0.052	1638
2650.02	29	0.017	1643

4 Jupiter occurrence rate around Solar Type Stars

4.1 Determining the population of Solar Type Stars

The first task in this analysis was to determine which stars qualify as "solar-type." I adopt several of the parameters used in Howard et. al. (2012). I required all stars in my analysis to have $4.0 \leq \log(g) \leq 4.9$ and $4100 \leq T_{\text{eff}} \leq 6100$. I did not adopt the Howard et. al. (2012) requirement that all stars in the analysis have a Kepler magnitude no greater than 15 mag.

I obtained the full Kepler Input Catalog from the NASA Exoplanet archive. This dataset contained 196677 stars. I then applied my criteria to eliminate the non solar type stars. The $\log(g)$ and T_{eff} requirements eliminated 875335 Kepler target stars from our sample. I then removed an additional 2447 stars that appeared suspicious. Each star had measured T_{eff} , $\log(g)$, metallicity, and radius that exactly matched the values for the Sun. Unlike the other stars in the dataset, these stars had no reported errors on any of these measurements. Until I understand what these stars are, I am not including them in my analysis. This left me with a total of 106895 solar type stars for my analysis.

4.2 Identifying the Jupiter type KOI's around solar type stars

I also needed to compile our sample of Jupiter type planets detected around stars in this population. I downloaded the entire list of KOI's from the NASA Exoplanet Archive. I first made a crude Jupiter type planet cutoff. Any KOI

with reported radius $\geq 8R_{\oplus}$ was considered a Jupiter type planet. All other KOI's were discarded. I imposed this lower radius limit in order to differentiate planet candidates large enough to be Jupiters from the rest of the planet candidates. The exact radius cutoff between ice giants like Neptune and gas giants like Jupiter is still ambiguous. I choose $8R_{\oplus}$ specifically to better compare my results to Howard et al. (2012). They calculated planet occurrence rate for different planet radii bins and used 8-32 R_{\oplus} as their giant type planet bin.

After making this cut, I examined the disposition of each remaining KOI. The Kepler team analyzes the lightcurve of transit-like signals and assigns a "disposition" to each object of interest. An object is either dispositioned as a false positive or as a planet candidate. In some cases, the object has not yet been dispositioned. I discarded all KOI's dispositioned as false positives. This removed an additional 708 KOI's. I also discarded the 214 KOI's in my sample that had not yet been dispositioned. This left us with 317 KOI's.

Finally, I correlated my remaining KOI's with my sample of stars and discarded any KOI whose host star was not in my sample. This left me with 157 Jupiter type planet candidates orbiting the solar type stars. From here, I began my analysis following the methodology outlined in Chapter 2.

4.3 Calculating Number of Stars Searched

I compared each planet to every solar type star to determine if it was detectable around that star. I used the same equation 2.5 to determine if S/N was high enough for a detection. The KOI data that I downloaded from the NASA Exoplanet Archive gave me the planet radius, and the stellar data I downloaded gave me the stellar radius. This allowed me to compute a transit depth for each planet-star pair using equation 2.3.

The stellar data also provided me with the list of quarters during which

each star was observed. Using the Kepler observing quarter lengths reported at <http://keplerscience.arc.nasa.gov/ArchiveSchedule.shtml>, I was able to determine the amount of time the star was observed. The orbital period was provided by the KOI data that I downloaded. This allowed me to calculate $N_{transits}$ using equation 2.4.

Finally, I needed to calculate σ_{CDPP} on the timescale of the planet's transit duration. The transit duration was included in my KOI data. I downloaded σ_{CDPP3} , σ_{CDPP6} , σ_{CDPP12} for each star during a given quarter from <http://archive.stsci.edu/pub/kepler/catalogs/>. I averaged σ_{CDPP3} , σ_{CDPP6} , σ_{CDPP12} for each star over all the quarters so that I had an average σ_{CDPP3} , σ_{CDPP6} , σ_{CDPP12} for each star. I then used a linear interpolation to estimate σ_{CDPP} for the transit duration timescale. I added an upper and lower bound to our interpolation. If the calculated σ_{CDPP} was less than the lowest σ_{CDPP} for any quarter, then I used the smallest individual quarter σ_{CDPP} instead. Similarly, if the calculated σ_{CDPP} was greater than the highest σ_{CDPP} , I defaulted to the largest σ_{CDPP} .

3 Hour CDP

Figure 4: Combined Differential Photometric Precision For Each Star Over 3 Hour Period

6 Hour CDP

Figure 5: Combined Differential Photometric Precision For Each Star Over 6 Hour Period

12 Hour CDPP

Figure 6: Combined Differential Photometric Precision For Each Star Over 12 Hour Period

Aside from a few exceptionally noisy stars, all stars have a Combined Differential Photometric Precision of less than 100,000 parts per million over 3,6, and 12 hour timescales. However, it is important to note that this is still a very wide range; even the normal σ_{CDPP} values can be as small as 10 ppm or as large as 100,000 ppm.

After obtaining a value of σ_{CDPP} on the transit timescale, $N_{transits}$, and the transit depth (δ), I used equation 2.5 to calculate the S/N for each planet-star pair, and then summed up all of the stars around which a given planet produced a signal with $S/N > 7.1$. This gave me a value of N_* for each planet.

Figure 7 shows that the number of stars searched is roughly the same for each planet. Each planet would be detected around almost the entire population of stars. This is not unexpected; all of these planets are quite large, which makes them easy to detect. In addition, most of the planets have extremely short orbital periods, so it would be easy to observe many transits, which reduces the S:N.

Ease of Detectability by Orbital Period

Figure 7: Planetary Orbital Period vs. Number of Stars Searched

4.4 Calculating Geometric Correction Factor

I needed to calculate a geometric correction factor for each planet. The KOI data provided me with a value of R_* for each planet's host star, as well as a value for the semi-major axis (a) of the planet's orbit derived from the transit lightcurve. I use the provided value of R_* but do not use the provided a . As described in section 3.4, deriving a value for semi-major axis using Kepler's 3rd law provides a much better estimate for the semi-major axis than the one derived from the lightcurve. I already have the mass of the host star from the stellar data we downloaded, and I have the orbital period from the KOI data. Therefore, it is simple to use Kepler's 3rd law to calculate the semi-major axis of the planet around its host star. Then I can calculate the geometric correction factor = $\frac{a}{R_*}$.

Once I have the geometric correction factor and number of stars searched for each planet, I calculate an occurrence rate for each individual planet using

equation 2.11.

Geometric Correction Factor

Figure 8: Geometric Correction Factor vs Planetary Orbital Period

The general trend is that a longer orbital period corresponds to a larger geometric correction factor. This is because a longer period implies a larger semi-major axis when the planets are around similar mass stars. Note that several planets have absurdly long periods ($> 500days$). These planets should be discussed later in this work.

4.5 Results

Here we present the results for our 157 KOI's.

Table 2: Solar Type Stars: Individual KOI Occurrence Rates

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K00001.01	14.4	2.47	1	1.13e-05	106892
K00017.01	11.07	3.23	1	1.37e-05	106891
K00020.01	17.6	4.44	1	1.35e-05	106892

Table 2: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K00022.01	11.27	7.89	3	2.45e-05	106890
K00094.01	11.4	22.34	4	3.58e-05	106888
K00127.01	10.93	3.58	2	1.55e-05	106891
K00128.01	11.97	4.94	2	1.78e-05	106891
K00135.01	10.56	3.02	1	1.24e-05	106891
K00183.01	12.4	2.68	1	1.39e-05	106891
K00188.01	8.3	3.8	2	2.24e-05	106887
K00189.01	9.88	30.36	9	8.42e-05	106877
K00190.01	17.2	12.26	3	2.5e-05	106891
K00191.01	11	15.36	5	4.53e-05	106887
K00195.01	11.7	3.22	2	1.55e-05	106891
K00196.01	9.4	1.86	1	1.1e-05	106891
K00200.01	8.6	7.34	3	3.01e-05	106887
K00201.01	10	4.23	2	1.53e-05	106890
K00203.01	14.82	1.49	1	8.4e-06	106893
K00206.01	8.1	5.33	2	1.8e-05	106888
K00217.01	11.7	3.91	2	2.02e-05	106891
K00340.01	16.8	23.67	5	5.08e-05	106893
K00372.01	8.52	125.63	18	0.0001724	106826
K00375.01	10.4	600.0	35	0.0003238	106636
K00377.01	8.28	19.27	5	4.8e-05	106869
K00377.02	8.22	38.91	8	7.66e-05	106852
K00398.01	8.1	51.85	12	0.0001147	106837
K00403.01	42	21.06	5	5.07e-05	106893

Table 2: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K00417.01	12	19.19	6	5.37e-05	106887
K00419.01	33	20.13	6	5.36e-05	106893
K00421.01	11.1	4.45	2	1.96e-05	106891
K00425.01	11.3	5.43	3	2.35e-05	106890
K00433.02	10.7	328.24	40	0.000377	106842
K00435.02	8.8	741.0	61	0.0005739	106634
K00458.01	8.3	53.72	8	7.89e-05	106836
K00490.02	9.4	341.0	46	0.0004276	106809
K00617.01	39	37.87	9	8.73e-05	106893
K00620.02	10	130.18	20	0.0001858	106848
K00682.01	10.8	562.14	38	0.0003569	106765
K00686.01	11.4	52.51	11	9.83e-05	106873
K00734.02	17.7	70.28	13	0.0001238	106889
K00753.01	9	19.9	6	5.5e-05	106870
K00763.01	12.6	19.65	5	4.57e-05	106889
K00767.01	12	2.82	1	1.39e-05	106891
K00771.01	15.7	670.65	54	0.0005023	106875
K00777.01	8.1	40.42	9	7.99e-05	106841
K00797.01	9.1	10.18	3	3.17e-05	106886
K00801.01	8.7	1.63	1	9.4e-06	106891
K00802.01	12.8	19.62	6	5.27e-05	106888
K00805.01	13.4	10.33	3	3e-05	106891
K00806.01	9.37	143.22	21	0.0001941	106843
K00806.02	14	60.32	12	0.000109	106887

Table 2: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K00809.01	12.1	1.59	1	9.2e-06	106892
K00815.01	33	34.84	8	7.74e-05	106893
K00824.01	9.6	15.38	6	5.15e-05	106884
K00830.01	9.77	3.53	2	2.19e-05	106890
K00833.01	44	3.95	2	1.69e-05	106893
K00838.01	13.2	4.86	2	1.98e-05	106891
K00846.01	16.2	27.81	7	6.41e-05	106890
K00850.01	8.4	10.53	4	3.71e-05	106878
K00855.01	12.2	41.41	10	9.02e-05	106884
K00858.01	15	13.61	4	3.86e-05	106891
K00871.01	19.8	12.94	4	3.91e-05	106892
K00883.01	11.12	2.69	2	1.77e-05	106891
K00889.01	9.4	8.88	4	3.49e-05	106887
K00895.01	11.4	4.41	2	1.66e-05	106891
K00897.01	11.5	2.05	1	1.17e-05	106891
K00908.01	8.5	4.71	2	1.9e-05	106887
K00913.01	11.1	4.08	2	1.94e-05	106891
K00918.01	10.1	39.64	10	9.08e-05	106875
K00931.01	11.1	3.86	2	1.94e-05	106891
K00998.01	28	161.79	23	0.0002115	106891
K01020.01	59	54.36	7	6.66e-05	106893
K01066.01	9.7	5.71	2	2.22e-05	106889
K01095.01	8.5	51.6	12	0.0001098	106834
K01096.01	10.3	414.0	45	0.0004211	106739

Table 2: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K01137.01	57	302.39	31	0.0002925	106893
K01192.01	48	2015.64	106	0.0009963	106892
K01193.01	10.2	119.06	15	0.0001421	106832
K01226.01	34	137.76	22	0.0002104	106892
K01227.01	28	2.16	1	1.28e-05	106893
K01258.03	18	148.27	24	0.0002215	106887
K01320.01	8.2	10.51	4	4.07e-05	106878
K01351.01	45	10.72	3	3.03e-05	106893
K01356.01	9.1	384.03	36	0.0003414	106780
K01385.01	64	18.61	5	4.79e-05	106893
K01387.01	47	23.8	6	5.74e-05	106893
K01421.01	9.4	485.0	47	0.0004388	106781
K01431.01	8.45	345.16	36	0.0003342	106612
K01456.01	9.4	7.89	2	2.15e-05	106888
K01465.01	8	9.77	4	3.4e-05	106874
K01466.01	9.3	281.56	41	0.0003847	106767
K01477.01	8.2	169.5	25	0.0002358	106739
K01483.01	53	185.95	26	0.0002389	106893
K01486.01	9.7	127.28	19	0.0001821	106845
K01496.01	11.1	36.13	8	7.33e-05	106874
K01546.01	9.5	0.92	1	7.7e-06	106891
K01549.01	74	29.48	6	5.65e-05	106893
K01552.01	10.8	77.63	13	0.0001231	106858
K01561.01	26	9.09	3	2.81e-05	106893

Table 2: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K01587.01	18	52.97	12	0.0001127	106890
K01645.01	22	41.17	10	9.17e-05	106891
K01675.01	9.1	14.62	5	4.51e-05	106877
K01691.01	44	35.15	8	7.74e-05	106893
K01773.01	44	83.1	13	0.000124	106893
K01782.01	35	15.42	5	4.7e-05	106893
K01787.01	8	98.72	16	0.0001533	106798
K01799.01	49	1.73	1	1.03e-05	106893
K01829.01	29	22.84	7	6.32e-05	106893
K01906.01	15	8.71	4	3.55e-05	106891
K01935.01	10.8	15.44	6	6.05e-05	106887
K01995.01	8.5	14.39	4	3.84e-05	106872
K02128.01	20	24.26	8	7.03e-05	106891
K02189.01	57	33.36	6	5.7e-05	106893
K02299.01	10.4	16.49	5	4.89e-05	106884
K02512.01	22	15.92	5	5.04e-05	106892
K02578.01	44	13.33	4	3.52e-05	106893
K02689.01	43	165.34	20	0.000187	106892
K02933.01	28	119.08	24	0.0002243	106891
K02996.01	24	15.93	5	5e-05	106892
K03320.01	21.622	85.06	15	0.0001437	106891
K03331.01	8.5376	18.17	6	5.31e-05	106877
K03334.01	26.915	95.18	20	0.0001839	106891
K03357.01	29.417	52.8	11	0.0001024	106892

Table 2: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K03385.01	45.39	54.06	9	8.42e-05	106893
K03449.01	25.12	62.13	13	0.0001175	106891
K03487.01	32.41	89.74	18	0.0001679	106892
K03527.01	58.27	76.82	16	0.0001458	106893
K03531.01	53.06	70.58	13	0.0001255	106893
K03545.01	31.4274	1.09	1	1.02e-05	106893
K03554.01	39.4209	394.68	43	0.0004024	106891
K03565.01	61.22	2.64	1	1.36e-05	106893
K03581.01	40.5391	10.99	4	3.99e-05	106893
K03602.01	30.91	249.36	26	0.000246	106891
K03605.01	23.28	178.27	28	0.0002662	106890
K03620.01	25.93	46.7	11	0.0001013	106892
K03626.01	49.18	44.15	10	9.05e-05	106893
K03641.01	21.51	178.41	27	0.0002548	106888
K03652.01	55.01	16.37	3	2.99e-05	106893
K03660.01	16.2768	174.77	27	0.0002498	106874
K03663.01	11.2899	282.53	27	0.0002571	106847
K03674.01	26.72	175.07	26	0.0002458	106891
K03675.01	35.153	20.84	6	5.64e-05	106893
K03678.01	9.1192	160.89	19	0.0001774	106841
K03680.01	10.672	141.24	21	0.0001987	106848
K03685.01	23.15	208.87	25	0.0002336	106889
K03696.01	24.67	181.85	24	0.0002202	106890
K03726.01	14.941	115.99	21	0.0001948	106877

Table 2: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K03765.01	23.5	0.87	1	1.02e-05	106893
K03767.01	16.779	6.71	3	2.7e-05	106892
K03771.01	13.981	5.8	2	2.2e-05	106891
K03784.01	14.65	23.87	5	4.77e-05	106890
K03787.01	9.17	141.73	18	0.0001656	106746
K03801.01	11.408	288.31	33	0.0003104	106820
K03830.01	13.6	1.03	1	8.4e-06	106893
K04939.01	8.585	281.33	37	0.0003481	106807
K05018.01	10.45	293.51	37	0.0003428	106739
K05478.01	38.849	351.29	39	0.0003654	106892

Several features of this dataset stand out. The geometric corrections are on average lower than those found in my reproduction of the Dressing, Charbonneau 2013 results. This is most likely because the solar type stars are much larger than the M Dwarfs. The geometric correction factor is $\frac{a}{R_*}$, so this larger stellar radius will create much lower geometric correction factors.

The number of stars searched is approximately 106890 for all of these planets, with very little variation. This is almost the full sample of stars (106895). This means that I must be calculating very high S/N for these planets around each star. Indeed, some of the S/N are as high as 1000. However, it is not unreasonable for the S/N of Jupiter type stars to be very high. Kepler is designed to detect Earth type planets transiting around solar type stars, so it is reasonable to assume that some Earth type planets have $S/N > 7.1$ around

these solar type stars. S/N is proportional to transit depth, and transit depth is proportional to R_p^2 . The radii of my planets are all at least $8R_\oplus$, so these planets should have S/N at least 100 times greater than Earth like planets. When that is taken into consideration, it is more reasonable for the S/N to be so high.

Figures 4 and 5 show that the characteristic dependence on orbital period and planetary radius is present in the number of stars searched, but it is simply a very weak effect. Most stars have low enough noise that any of the planets could have been detected around them. The largest varying factor in calculating the S/N for each planet-star pair is the σ_{CDPP} of the star. As explained earlier, the σ_{CDPP} for different stars can vary by as much as 4 orders of magnitude. Outside of a few outliers, planetary period is between 1 and 300 days and S/N , and planetary radius is between 10 to 80 earth radii. S/N has a linear dependence on σ_{CDPP} and planetary radius, but only depends on the square root of the planetary radius. Therefore, the variability in σ_{CDPP} is the dominant factor in whether a star-planet pair produces a detectable transit. The planet's parameters only have a minor effect, which explains why the number of stars searched is so similar for each planetary candidate.

The overall occurrence rate for the whole population can be obtained by summing all of the individual occurrence rates. This gives us an overall occurrence rate of 0.0186 Jupiter type planets per solar type star.

5 Jupiter occurrence rate around M Dwarf Stars

This was the shortest part of the analysis. The number of confirmed M Dwarf stars observed by Kepler is very low, so this made for a very small analysis. Ideally, I would have more data to supplement this section, since the small size of the dataset makes it difficult to make strong conclusions about the Jupiter

occurrence rate around the M Dwarf stars.

5.1 Determining the Population of M Dwarf Stars

As discussed in Chapter 3, the M Dwarf stars are mostly misclassified in the Kepler Input Catalog (KIC). Furthermore, I face the difficulty of differentiating between M Dwarf stars and evolved giant stars which have similar effective temperatures. Finding a sample of M Dwarf stars is much more difficult than finding a sample for the Solar type or high mass type stars. For this analysis, I use the stars classified as M Dwarfs in Dressing, Charbonneau (2013). Unfortunately, this likely does not include all of the M Dwarfs observed by Kepler, since their analysis was done on only the first 6 quarters of Kepler data. However, this does not make the resulting occurrence rate invalid; it simply restricts the population about which our results can have meaning. I can take a planet occurrence rate for any population of stars as long as that population is carefully defined. The planet occurrence rate results from this subset of the Kepler M Dwarfs can be generalized to the full sample of M Dwarfs as long as this subset does not differ substantially from the full population of Kepler M Dwarfs. We assume that to be true. In the future, it would be helpful to expand this analysis to contain more of the Kepler M Dwarfs.

My sample of stars is the same sample used for reproducing the Dressing, Charbonneau (2013) results in Chapter 3. This is a population of 3892 stars.

5.2 Identifying the Jupiter type KOI's around M Dwarf stars

I found 5 KOI's with $R_p > 8M_\oplus$ around this population of stars. 3 of these KOI's (K00254.01, K02156.01) were in the Dressing, Charbonneau 2013 analysis. The other three (K02842.01, K02842.02, K03414.01) are new to this occur-

rence rate analysis. Adding the additional 11 quarters of Kepler Data that were unavailable for the Dressing, Charbonneau 2013 analysis has provided several additional planets. This briefly shows the expected behavior when adding more data: number of stars searched should go up for each planet, since the possible observed number of transits will be higher, as each star is observed longer. At the same time, the number of planets detected will go up, so the occurrence rate will remain about the same.

The only exception to this would be a transit survey that has detected all of the transiting planets in the stellar population it is observing. In that case, as the stellar population is observed longer, the number of stars searched could rise while the number of planets detected remained constant, leading to the calculated planet occurrence rate actually decreasing.

5.3 Calculating Occurrence Rate

After defining our stellar population and finding the relevant KOI's, I followed the same procedure used in Chapter 4 to calculate the Jupiter Type Planet Occurrence Rate. The results are shown in Table 3. Note that we are using the full 17 quarters of Kepler data to determine the total time each star was observed. Transit depth, σ_{CDPP} on the transit timescale, and the geometric correction factor are calculated using the same methodology outlined in Chapter 4.

Table 3: M Dwarf Stars: Individual KOI Occurrence Rates

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K00254.01	10.74	2.46	37	0.0095068	3891
K02156.01	11.32	2.85	48	0.0122965	3891
K02842.01	25.0	1.57	32	0.0081353	3892
K02842.02	26.0	5.15	70	0.0179928	3892

K03414.01 18.5 27.01 189 0.0484278 3891

Again, all KOI's have very similar number of stars searched. In this case, it is either 3891 or 3892 for every KOI. This should not be particularly surprising, especially after the seeing the results from the solar type stars: if it was trivially easy to detect Jupiter type planets around the solar type stars, it should be even easier around the smaller M dwarf type stars. The geometric correction factors are all very large. This is easily explained by the semi-major axes of these planets' orbits being much larger than the radius of the M Dwarf stars. Since number of stars searched is so uniform, the geometric correction factor is the main term differentiating each KOI's individual occurrence rate.

Summing over the whole data set gives a Jupiter type planet occurrence rate around this subset of the Kepler M Dwarfs of 0.0963 Jupiters per star.

6 Jupiter occurrence rate around High Mass Stars

6.1 Determining the Population of High Mass Stars

I choose the population of "high mass stars" as the O,B,A, and F stars, and used cutoffs of $T_{eff} > 6100K$ and $logg \geq 3$. This methodology gave a population of 55716 stars. For the high mass stars, it is sufficient to use just T_{eff} as an identifier. Unlike for the M Dwarfs, I can be confident that there are very few non main sequence stars contaminating the sample. It is possible that there may be some supergiants within this T_{eff} and log g cutoff but they should be rare enough to not significantly impact our results.

6.2 Identifying the Jupiter type KOI's high mass stars

Comparing the list of KOI's with $R_p > 8R_{Earth}$ to this stellar population gave 111 planet candidates. This process was straightforward and had no complications.

6.3 Calculating Jupiter Type Planet Occurrence Rate around the High Mass Stars

Again, I used the methodology described in Chapter 4 to calculate the occurrence rate. The results are summarized in Table 4 below.

Table 4: High Mass Stars: Individual KOI Occurrence Rates

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K00002.01	22.3	2.2	1	1.25e-05	55711
K00010.01	15.9	3.52	1	2.13e-05	55704
K00012.01	13.4	17.86	4	6.33e-05	55679
K00013.01	23	1.76	0	8.3e-06	55711
K00018.01	17.4	3.55	1	1.88e-05	55708
K00098.01	10	6.79	1	2.48e-05	55671
K00100.01	21.8	9.97	1	2.26e-05	55707
K00131.01	9	5.01	2	3.24e-05	55660
K00138.01	23.3	48.94	6	0.0001068	55697
K00186.01	12.3	3.24	2	2.82e-05	55696
K00192.01	10.1	10.29	3	6.24e-05	55647
K00193.01	14	37.59	8	0.0001465	55650
K00199.01	11	3.27	1	2.59e-05	55691
K00202.01	11.2	1.72	1	1.73e-05	55697

Table 4: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K00208.01	11.3	3.0	1	2.47e-05	55695
K00209.01	8.75	50.79	9	0.0001591	55478
K00211.01	9.6	124.04	17	0.000302	55158
K00225.01	50	0.84	1	1.23e-05	55716
K00351.01	9.8	331.64	32	0.0005836	55107
K00353.01	9.1	152.1	16	0.0002946	55072
K00366.01	10.6	75.11	5	8.15e-05	55409
K00368.01	18.9	110.32	10	0.0001871	55687
K00410.01	45	7.22	3	4.49e-05	55714
K00422.01	15	480.0	42	0.0007529	55389
K00423.01	9.8	21.09	4	6.59e-05	55588
K00466.01	8	9.39	3	5.88e-05	55547
K00601.02	9	11.68	4	6.96e-05	55567
K00611.01	12.2	3.25	1	2.58e-05	55695
K00625.01	47	38.14	4	7.04e-05	55711
K00680.01	8	8.6	3	4.89e-05	55625
K00698.01	10.87	12.72	2	4.4e-05	55645
K00728.01	11.2	7.19	3	4.71e-05	55672
K00760.01	10.9	4.96	2	3.76e-05	55679
K00772.01	13.1	61.26	10	0.0001884	55614
K00774.01	16	7.44	3	5.08e-05	55697
K00823.01	8.7	1.03	1	1.3e-05	55692
K00856.01	15	39.75	9	0.0001571	55670
K00890.01	8.2	8.1	3	5.1e-05	55599

Table 4: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K00929.01	8.7	6.49	2	4.16e-05	55640
K00969.01	49	17.51	4	7.64e-05	55713
K00976.01	89	52.57	7	0.0001267	55715
K01067.01	37	185.02	23	0.0004115	55701
K01074.01	11.1	3.77	2	2.9e-05	55690
K01089.01	9.7	86.68	14	0.0002453	55433
K01242.01	52	99.64	14	0.0002471	55709
K01268.01	12	268.94	31	0.000556	55214
K01271.01	10.5	161.86	16	0.0002942	55349
K01288.01	10.87	117.93	16	0.0002849	55356
K01335.01	8.6	127.83	11	0.0001994	55243
K01353.01	18.6	125.87	12	0.000212	55664
K01391.01	8.8	7.98	3	5.29e-05	55606
K01426.03	14.7	150.02	20	0.000354	55527
K01452.01	23	1.15	1	9e-06	55712
K01463.01	16.29	580.0	24	0.0004342	55504
K01474.01	9.3	69.73	9	0.0001675	55284
K01547.01	11.3	30.69	7	0.0001268	55582
K01558.01	36	32.5	8	0.0001375	55709
K01658.01	12.35	1.54	1	1.25e-05	55702
K01761.01	9.1	10.13	3	5.55e-05	55601
K01771.01	65	91.06	14	0.0002588	55712
K01783.01	8.5	134.48	20	0.0003604	54927
K01793.01	32	3.26	2	3.01e-05	55712

Table 4: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K01798.01	9.1	12.96	4	7.07e-05	55565
K02042.01	9.5	63.07	5	9.6e-05	55404
K02513.01	12.6	19.01	5	8.91e-05	55654
K02577.01	28	18.56	4	7.35e-05	55709
K02679.01	14.1	110.76	15	0.0002714	55568
K03342.01	37.3331	42.4	9	0.0001643	55709
K03386.01	39.96	34.53	7	0.000131	55709
K03411.01	13.26	26.84	6	0.0001134	55641
K03413.01	56.4	49.61	10	0.0001729	55712
K03419.01	52.14	58.59	8	0.0001495	55711
K03467.01	29.543	33.94	7	0.000129	55708
K03506.01	62.33	12.63	2	4.1e-05	55715
K03515.01	61.6494	82.14	11	0.0002021	55712
K03533.01	58.21	152.15	21	0.0003769	55712
K03541.01	54.867	421.43	25	0.0004423	55708
K03557.01	42.386	243.82	24	0.0004288	55707
K03560.01	37.9243	1.5	1	1.56e-05	55715
K03573.01	42.67	43.56	7	0.0001336	55709
K03583.01	69.49	210.31	15	0.0002668	55711
K03606.01	59.17	2.18	1	1.66e-05	55716
K03608.01	29.75	244.83	28	0.0005058	55687
K03611.01	62.2	10.44	3	6.04e-05	55715
K03617.01	115.784	1.68	1	9.4e-06	55716
K03627.02	23.08	8.53	3	5.51e-05	55709

Table 4: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K03647.01	45.4	20.43	5	8.64e-05	55712
K03649.01	65.36	1.3	1	1.16e-05	55716
K03681.01	22.0667	217.83	12	0.0002103	55687
K03683.01	9.3343	214.31	20	0.0003581	55228
K03689.01	13.3479	5.24	2	3e-05	55696
K03690.01	27.88	12.89	3	5.16e-05	55709
K03692.01	14.322	1.16	1	1.03e-05	55708
K03709.01	20.89	205.58	27	0.0004889	55650
K03715.01	29.27	9.85	3	4.84e-05	55709
K03717.01	19.13	227.66	26	0.0004694	55613
K03720.01	28.84	213.4	19	0.0003449	55691
K03721.01	19.05	6.41	2	3.73e-05	55705
K03728.01	20.5203	5.55	1	1.26e-05	55708
K03735.01	74.6	8.1	2	3.87e-05	55716
K03742.01	74.52	1.41	1	1.49e-05	55716
K03780.01	16.68	27.96	5	9.23e-05	55681
K03783.01	13.8	197.14	15	0.0002691	55368
K03815.01	8.325	4.74	2	3.57e-05	55627
K03837.01	9.14	7.44	2	4.2e-05	55636
K04959.01	50.59	420.93	35	0.0006242	55708
K04980.01	77.8045	2.98	1	1.92e-05	55716
K05023.01	76.4	73.34	10	0.0001729	55714
K05052.01	20.1	155.05	9	0.0001662	55669
K05243.01	105.22	17.75	2	4.18e-05	55716

Table 4: continued

KOI	R_p	Period	Geometric Correction	Occurrence Rate	Stars Searched
K05774.01	49.8002	1.21	1	9.2e-06	55716

The number of stars searched is still quite uniform in this data set. Most KOI's would have been detected around approximately 55700 of the stars in the population. However, this population does have a larger difference in number of stars searched than the other data sets. The highest is 55716 (the entire dataset) and the lowest is 54927. This is a difference of 789. It should be expected that the greatest discrepancy between number of stars searched is in this data set. The reason that the other data sets had such uniform distributions for number of stars searched was that every planet was detectable around nearly every star. But finally, with the high mass stars, there is a population in which many stars are too large to produce strong transit signals even for a Jupiter type planet. For the smaller Jupiter type planets with large periods, this can make their transits undetectable around several hundred of these larger radii stars.

The geometric correction factors are noticeably small compared to the other data sets. This is due to the larger radii of the stars in this population. If we recall that geometric correction factor is $\frac{a}{R_*}$, it is apparent that increasing the stellar radii will lead to a smaller geometric correction factor.

Summing over all of the occurrence rates for this population gives an overall occurrence rate of 0.0164 Jupiter type planets per star. I will discuss this occurrence rate and compare it to the others in the following chapter.

7 Final Results: Concluding Where Jupiter Type Planets are Most Common

The resulting overall Jupiter occurrence rates for each population are:

M Dwarfs: 0.0963

Solar Type: 0.0186

High Mass: 0.0164

This is certainly not the expected result. Following planet accretion theory, one would expect larger planets to form alongside larger stars. From these results, it seems that opposite is true: the population of M Dwarfs has the highest occurrence rate for Jupiters at 1 Jupiter for every 10 stars. The Solar Type and High Mass star categories have similar occurrence rates of approximately 1.5 Jupiter for every 100 stars. Can this data be used to say anything definitive? Probably not yet. There are several compounding factors to consider.

7.1 Ruling out False Positives

We have not investigated false positives in the earlier parts of this analysis. As mentioned earlier Morton, Johnson (2011) showed that the Kepler planet candidates generally have very low false positive rates but the Jupiter type planet candidates have much higher false positive rates. Although we did not take false positive probability into account in our analysis I did try to remove the false positives I could easily identify. Many of the KOI's can be identified as false positives just by their overly large radii. Figure 9 shows all confirmed exoplanets discovered by surveys other than Kepler.

I used Figure 7 to develop an upper radius limit for a Jupiter type planet. Since it was very rare for a confirmed exoplanet to have $R_p > 20R_{\oplus}$ I decided to classify all planet candidates over $20R_{\oplus}$ as false positives. This is a somewhat

Figure 9: Radius vs. Mass for Confirmed Exoplanets

Note that exoplanets discovered by Kepler are not included. Therefore, most of these planets were discovered by radial velocity surveys which partially explains why most of the planets are very large. The planet with the largest listed radius is HAT-P-32 with a radius of $23R_{\oplus}$.

conservative cut since there are at least a few confirmed exoplanets above this radius cutoff. I decided not to worry about this too much. I knew that $20R_{\oplus}$ was at least a safe limit under which it is plausible that the planet candidates are planets. I decided that the occurrence rate of Jupiter type planets with $R_p < 20R_{\oplus}$ would be a more interesting occurrence rate than the original rates I calculated.

In addition I wanted to set a reasonable period limit as well. I decided to cut all planet candidates with $P > 150$ days. For the remaining planet candidates we can be relatively sure that Kepler would have had time to observe 2 or 3

of a candidate’s transits. I also make an even more conservative cut of $P < 50$ days to investigate the occurrence rate of “Hot Jupiters.” This also matches the period cut made in the Howard et. al. (2012) analysis allowing for a better comparison with their results.

Finally, I manually investigated the planet candidate lightcurves to see if they exhibited any obvious signs of a false positive. In particular I looked for signs that the “planet candidate” was actually a star orbiting around the host star. I looked for signs such as V-shaped transit curves, and microlensing effects. This analysis was not done in any mathematical way; it was entirely a physical inspection process. In the future I think further investigation of the light curves would greatly improve these occurrence rate estimates. A more detailed analysis of the individual lightcurves is certainly feasible since there are only a few hundred Jupiter type planet candidates to examine. Below I present the lightcurve for a confirmed planet, KOI 254.01, as well as the lightcurve for a planet I determined to be a false positive, KOI 3414.01.

Figure 10: KOI 254.01: Phase Folded Lightcurve

This is a confirmed planet: Johnson et. al. (2012). The Phase Folded Lightcurve means that all observations have been plotted with their normalized flux on the y axis and their time from transit center on the x axis. This allows the reviewer to see all of the data simultaneously “folded” into one transit period. The shape of this lightcurve is typical of a planetary transit. There is an ingress period during which the flux gradually drops as the planet begins to pass in front of the star. The bottom dip is also somewhat curved; the planet blocks more light as it crosses the center parts of the star. Finally there is an egress period mirroring the ingress period as the planet passes off the other side of the star. This lightcurve is a good reference for what a planetary transit generally should look like.

Figure 11: KOI 3414.01: Phase Folded Lightcurve

This planet candidate is most likely a false positive. The lightcurve exhibits a particularly V-shaped profile: the ingress and egress are basically straight down with little curvature and the bottom part of the transit does not show as much of the rounded features present in the KOI 254.01 lightcurve. However, this could simply be indicative of a very high inclination orbit. The high flux points during the middle of the transit are particularly out of place. It seems that the flux actually increases as the transiting object passes over the center of the star. I believe this is due to a microlensing event caused by the transiting object. This implies the transiting object is a much more massive object than a planet perhaps a White Dwarf star. This lightcurve had several signs of being a false positive so this planet was excluded from the second phase of my analysis.

7.2 Results with Additional Cuts

After removing planets that did not make the radius cut, period cut, or appeared to be false positives I calculated new occurrence rates.

Period < 150 days:

M Dwarf Stars: 0.0095068 (1 planet)

Solar Type Stars: 0.00498 (86 planets)

High Mass Stars: 0.00556 (55 planets)

This analysis represents our final occurrence rates once false positives have been removed; these occurrence rates represent our most complete analysis of the Kepler data. The comparative difference between categories mostly matches the results before we made our false positive or period cuts. The high mass stars and solar type stars have roughly equivalent occurrence rates and the M dwarf type stars have much higher occurrence rates than either of them. The M Dwarf stars have just under twice the occurrence rate of the other categories and before the cuts it was about five times larger than the other categories. This is the only sample in which the high mass stars have a higher occurrence rate than the solar type stars.

Our occurrence rates are quite low compared to Jupiter occurrence rates from Radial velocity surveys which are typically around 1.2 percent (see section 1.6.3). The metallicity of our stars may be the reason for this discrepancy. It is possible that the Kepler stars are lower in metallicity than the populations observed in these surveys. Further investigation into the differences between our occurrence rates and those found by radial velocity surveys would be very interesting.

Period < 50 days:

M Dwarf Stars: 0.0095068 (1 planet)

Solar Type Stars: 0.00282 (73 planets)

High Mass Stars: 0.00215 (40 planets)

This analysis represents the “hot jupiters.” Once again the solar type and high mass type stars have very similar occurrence rates although once again the solar type stars has the higher occurrence rate. The M Dwarf occurrence rate has remained the same since no planets were removed from that sample by the cut. The M Dwarf results should not be taken too seriously; with just one planet in the analysis the results are far from representative of the true population of Jupiter type planets around M Dwarf stars.

The result that the high mass stars and solar type stars have such similar occurrence rates is largely explained by how we have defined those two categories. The “solar type” stars are K,G stars which have masses ranging from 0.8-1.4 M_{\odot} . The “high mass” stars are F,A, and B stars encompassing a mass range of 1.4 - 16 M_{\odot} . These groups should have very different mass distributions. However most of our ”high mass” stars are actually on the lower end of this mass range. Our ”high mass” stars sample is primarily composed of F,A stars. Only 349 of the 55,5716 stars have $T_{eff} \geq 10,000$.

Although we have made the same period cut as Howard et. al. 2011 our Jupiter occurrence rate is much lower than their rate of 0.013. This begs further investigation but is mostly likely due to our better treatment of the possibility of false positives.

It would be useful to define a group of higher mass B stars and investigate the Jupiter type planet occurrence rate around those stars. Unfortunately there are only 349 stars with $T_{eff} > 10,000K$ and none of them hosts a planet candidate.

Figure 12: Kepler Target Stars

This shows the Kepler Target Stars binned by T_{eff} . The blue lines show our upper and lower T_{eff} cuts for the solar type stars. The upper cut for the solar type stars is also the lower cut for the high mass stars. Note that the majority of the high mass stars have $T_{eff} < 10,000$ Kelvin. This shows the majority of the stars in our high mass stars sample are F and A type stars which have solar masses ranging from 1-2 M_{\odot} .

This prevents us from investigating truly high mass stars.

However our occurrence rates do shed show that Jupiter type planet occurrence rate is not significantly higher for $2M_{\odot}$ stars than it is for $1M_{\odot}$ stars. If there is a correlation between Jupiter type occurrence rate and stellar mass it certainly is not strong enough to make a difference over this very small mass range. Unfortunately due to limited number of Kepler target stars outside of the K,G,F, and A categories we are unable to investigate this correlation over large mass ranges where a correlation would be more obvious if it exists.

7.2.1 Metallicity

Planet formation theory predicts Jupiter type planets can form in 2 ways. The first is a “top down” process in which part of the protoplanetary disk becomes gravitationally unstable and collapses in on itself, forming a large planet that is predominantly made of gas. The second is a ”top up” mechanism that is similar to the process proposed for terrestrial planets: dust particles in the disk collide and coalesce into small rocks that collide and coalesce into larger rocks, until finally a terrestrial planet is created. However, if the planet grows very quickly, it may reach a sufficient mass to accrete gas from the disk before the disk dissipates. In this case, a giant Jupiter-type planet is formed as the growing rocky planet sucks up all of the disk gas along its orbital path. In this work, I will not argue for which is the dominant mechanism in forming Jupiter type planets, but the possibility that the core accretion model is the dominant mechanism implies that I need to be worried about metallicity of the stellar populations we compare.

The rate at which a rocky core can form is largely dependent on the amount of non-gaseous material in the disk. The metallicity of a planet’s host star allows one to trace how much non-hydrogen and helium content existed in the protoplanetary disk. It is important when comparing planet occurrence rates across stellar populations to take into account the metallicities of each population, and this is something I have not accounted for in this analysis. This would be an important topic to investigate to improve this analysis. Unfortunately the Kepler Input Catalog only provides estimates of metallicity derived from photometry of each Kepler target star. In order to investigate the metallicity of these Kepler target stars I would need some other source of metallicity data.

7.3 Conclusion

Despite my inability to determine whether there is a correlation between Jupiter occurrence rate and host star mass on large mass scales I have been able to show there is no noticeable correlation on small mass scales of $0.8-2 M_{\odot}$. In addition, we have provided occurrence rate calculations from the Kepler data that still deserve further investigation, particularly in their comparison with similar occurrence rates calculated from radial velocity surveys.

Additional data for very high and very low mass stars will be needed to investigate this correlation over large mass scales. TESS (Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite) will perform a transit survey on many of the stars closest to Earth which will definitely help make up for the lack of low mass planet data. Combining radial velocity data may also provide another way to push this work forward.

The code I have developed for this project has any possible applications for calculating occurrence rates for different subsets of the Kepler stars and planet candidates. The ability to enter in simple cuts for the Kepler planets and stars and automatically obtain a occurrence rate has many uses aside from investigating this particular correlation.

This project has been extremely educational for me. I have learned a huge amount about the biases inherent in transit surveys and the correct way to interpret the results of such a survey. I am extremely grateful to my advisor, Professor John Johnson, for advice and guidance throughout this project. I would also like to thank Professor Moran for his frequent advice and work to motivate me. Finally I would like to thank Courtney Dressing for helping me to understand how planet occurrence rates are calculated. Her help was instrumental in my efforts to write code that could perform this calculation and the time she took to answer my questions as I tried to reproduce the Dressing,

Charbonneau (2013) results helped me grasp the complexities of this type of analysis.

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